

Application of Target Costing in Determining the Selling Price at Suwar-Suwir Producers in Jember (Study at UD. Purnama Jati and UD. Mutiara Rasa)

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to know the determination of selling price of suwar-suwir at UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa using the target costing. This research is a descriptive qualitative research using interview, observation, and documentation methods, and using primary and secondary data. Based on the results of research conducted at UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa shows that the application of target costing through value engineering, the both of companies can still get a profit from selling price per unit of product that is 30% at UD Purnama Jati and 20% at UD Mutiara Rasa. So, if UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa want to increase the selling price of their suwar-suwir, the both of companies will get a greater profit. Therefore, it can be concluded that the application of target costing in this research shows success because the both of companies can determine the lowest selling price among the current market prices, but they still get the desired profit and can manage production costs well.

1. INTRODUCTION

The more rapid development of the economy in Indonesia, which is getting more advanced, making economic activities increasingly stretched. The life of the economy coupled with the emergence of new demands from consumers gave rise to producers to meet consumer demand. These opportunities are certainly a motivation for new producers to join in the show. Indirectly this raises competition between the two old producers and new producers. Not only from the old producers and new producers, competition also arises from fellow producers who are in one type of industry. One industry that is experiencing significant development is an industry engaged in food and beverage production. Eating and drinking are primary needs for humans so that the level of

demand will always increase. Therefore, producers are required to be able to increase competitiveness in their businesses.

Conceiving to food, there have been many emerging industries in Indonesia that focus on producing food. Ranging from heavy foods to snacks. Especially in Jember City, there are also many similar food industries. The author will focus on the snack industry. The industry in Jember that the writer wants to develop is a small industry that produces snacks. More specifically, the author will focus on industries engaged in the processing of tape singkong processed snack products because the development of tape singkong processed products turns out to be developing so rapidly that the City of Jember is known as the suwir-suwir city. There are various products that are produced from processed tape singkong. In its development, tape singkong is

reprocessed into various products, including suwar-suwir products. The development of suwar-suwir as a characteristic of the City of Jember creates a new competitive value for the suwar-suwir industry. This opportunity must be exploited by suwar-suwir producers, thus demanding suwar-suwir producers to be more efficient and economical in their production processes. Not only that, they also need to always improve the quality of their products and create more competitive prices on the market.

Discussing about Suwar-Suwir, Suwar-Suwir is a snack that originates from Jember Regency. The main raw material for making suwar-suwir is a tape which is fermented from cassava and then processed into such a way that it becomes a snack. Suwar-suwir almost has something in common with candy because they both have a sweet taste. Although suwar-suwir are similar to candy, suwar-suwir textures are not as hard as candy. Since long ago, suwar-suwir have been a typical food and can only be found in the City of Jember. It has survived until now, so that many consumers from outside the City if they want to enjoy suwar-suwir have to come to Jember City. UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa is one of the producers that has long been known by the people of Jember to produce tape singkong processed snacks such as suwar-suwir, considering the number of their products that have been circulating in the market. This indication is based on the ease of finding both products in stores and outlets selling cassava processed foods, even recently their products have entered franchises such as Indomaret. More and more industries in Jember are engaged in the production of tape singkong processed snack foods, of course threatening the sustainability of their businesses. The author has the motivation to assist them in formulating strategies in the face of competition in this suwar-suwir industry. This was stated in the determination of selling prices through calculation and accounting methods.

These calculations and methods can ultimately be used by UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa as their respective strategies to improve competitiveness so that the products they produce remain the people's choice. The intended strategy is not only from the taste they create and the quality of their products, but also from determining the costs incurred during the production process until the product is ready for sale. In relation to the selling price, the producer must determine the cost correctly and calculate correctly so that in determining the selling price,

the company does not experience a substantial loss. The right and correct cost calculation will help the company in making selling price decisions.

According to Irma and Wahyu (2017, 145), "to determine this selling price if it is too low will harm the company and will affect the company's business continuity such as continuous losses. Conversely, sales that are too high can also resulting in the run of consumers".

Price determination need to be considered so that they can still get the desired the profit without reducing the quality of these products and in order to remain able to compete with other industries engaged in the same field. The author will focus on the selling price determination strategy, which is based on the still many producers (especially suwar-suwir) who in determining the selling price are still racing against the costs incurred during production after which they determine the selling price prevailing in the market.

Anugerah (2015) states, "that in fact, the determination of selling prices based on the amount of costs incurred cannot survive in the market. This can occur because company managers first calculate the costs incurred to produce goods, then determined the selling price based on costs incurred".

The focus of the problem in this research is when making a product at a price that is already known in advance but does not reduce the quality and components that will be given to consumers and still produce the desired level of profit. Of course this will be an interesting topic to research.

UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa determine the selling price of each product by making a product first, then determining the selling price following the market price. This kind of strategy is not new and is commonly practiced by many producers and can be run effective if the market price is high or the price is not decreasing. This strategy backfired for the two producers if the prevailing market price has decreased. This strategy can have a negative impact especially on losses for producers. On that basis, the author will incorporate an accounting approach to creating new strategies which certainly have their own advantages over the previous strategy.

According to Rudianto (2013, 145), "these advantages that is the product selling price is determined first, while the profit margin target and the target cost are set later. If the profit margin target is increased, then the company must make savings in production costs as well as non-production costs to achieve the target cost set based on the selling price".

This new strategy also brings a positive impact that the company can achieve the desired level of profit. This approach is called the target costing.

"Target costing is a method of determining the cost of production in which the company first determines the production costs to be incurred based on competitive market prices, so the company can obtain the expected profit" (Rudianto 2013, 145).

In this target costing method, the company's production flow will be changed, no longer making its products and then determining the cost of its products and selling prices and then marketing it to the public, but the company must first determine the cost of its products then make the product in accordance with the specified target cost based on the selling price and desired level of profit.

Caroline and Wokas (2016) states," that the determination of costs using target costing is based on the selling price and desired profit, in applying this method the company does not see the actual costs incurred to produce a product because the target costing, costs are before it happened the design and process production".

According to Johan (2014), " with target costing, companies can design a product or service that can meet the needs of consumers while simultaneously achieving company profit targets, because target costing considers all product costs in the product life cycle, and aims to reduce total cost of a product".

After the company knows the cost target that has been considered for production, the next step is to produce the goods. The goal is to still be able to produce a product that is able to compete. This step can help companies to manage costs well. Target costing also has a good impact on the company because by setting the selling price at the beginning of the process, the company is still able to compete with competitors without having to worry that the desired profit level will decrease. In addition, with this target costing method, all costs incurred to produce a product are in accordance with expectations and do not reduce the quality and desired profit levels. This new strategy, of course, contributes to both producers in terms of production efficiency, that is the exactness of prices to be released to the market. This strategy can be a consideration for producers in determining prices when market prices decline.

"Thus, the target costing system makes the company more competitive, because it is a form of general strategy in competition when facing very tight competition where even a small price difference can move consumers to turn to other products or substitute products." (Rudianto, 2013:145).

2. RESEARCH METHOD

Types of Research

This research is a type of qualitative research using descriptive methods. Descriptive qualitative research is research on problems in the form of current facts from a population which includes an assessment of the attitudes or opinions of individuals, organizations, circumstances, or procedures (Anggito and Setiawan 2018, 82). The purpose of descriptive qualitative research is to describe situations or phenomena as they are and to describe systematically, factually, and accurately about the facts and characteristics of objects being studied appropriately.

Research Location

This research was conducted in two places, that is:

1. UD Purnama Jati

Located on Bungur Street No. 9, Darwo Timur, Gebang, Patrang Sub-district, Jember District.

2. UD Mutiara Rasa

Located on Cendrawasih Street No. 60, Pancakarya, Ajung Sub-district, Jember District.

Data Types and Sources

The type of data used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained directly from original sources related to research. Primary data is also the most important source of data from research. Primary data related to this study were obtained through interviews with interested parties in this study, namely the owners of UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa. Secondary data is data obtained indirectly or through intermediary media such as books, records, available evidence, and other archives relating to research. Secondary data obtained for this study are quantitative data expressed in numerical form. Data can be in the form of reports related to costs, financial statements, and others. And obtained from qualitative data that is data or documents in the form of description or information and not in the form of numbers, such as a general description of the company, the company's current condition, and other supporting data relating to research.

Method of collecting data

Data collection methods generally consist of three types, namely, interviews, observation, and documentation. In this study to get a comprehensive picture and accurate information, the researchers used interview, observation, and documentation methods. In this study, researchers conducted direct interviews with those involved with the research problem, namely to the owners of UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa. Observations made in this study by making direct observations to the research object namely UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa about the condition of the company, company activities, how the production process that occurs in the company, starting from product design, purchasing raw materials, and production processes to finished until the product is ready to sell. The documentation in this research is to collect information in the form of raw material cost data, direct labor cost data, overhead data, and other documents that support this research.

Data Validity Testing

In this study, researchers used data triangulation. Data triangulation uses various data sources, such as documents, archives, interviews, observations or results also by interviewing more than one subject that is considered to have a different point of view. The researcher uses the results of the interview method and direct observation compared with information obtained from the results of the documentation to verify the truth of the information received from the source. This step is also useful for obtaining reliable information and a complete picture of information from objects related to this research.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Production Process and Suwar-Suwir Production Costs

1. UD Purnama Jati

UD Purnama Jati manufactures suwar-suwir original or commonly called suwar-suwir lapis. In the suwar-suwir lapis owned by UD Purnama Jati not given fruit flavorings and there are 4 kinds of colors that is red, green, yellow, and chocolate. One time suwar-suwir production, UD Purnama Jati requires 18 kg of tape singkong and 14 kg of sugar. Under normal circumstances, UD Purnama Jati produces suwar-suwir as much as 25x production per month, so the need for tape singkong as much as 450 kg and 350 kg of sugar. The suwar-suwir production process at UD Purnama Jati is carried out in several stages.

First, clean the tape singkong with its wicks or fibers so that during the cooking process no fibers are mixed. Second, mixing the tape singkong dough with sugar so that it merges at the time of production then cooked until it is a suwar-suwir dough. The process of cooking suwar-suwir dough takes approximately 1.5 hours. Third, mix sweetened condensed milk and chocolate paste as needed. Fourth, stir the suwar-suwir dough until evenly distributed and then printed on a roll table that has been provided. Fifth, cut the suwar-suwir dough according to its size. Sixth, do bindery suwar-suwir per seed with plastic. Seventh, do the packaging process the company wants as well as by labelling or sticker to be marketed to consumers. The total production cost of UD Purnama Jati can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Total Production Costs of UD Purnama Jati

Types of Products	Total Cost
Suwar-Suwir Lapis	Rp 1.353.570
Mica Packaging (1 Kg)	
Suwar-Suwir Lapis	Rp 1.343.400
Mica Packaging (500 Grams)	

2. UD Mutiara Rasa

There are five types of suwar-suwir flavors produced by UD Mutiara Rasa, that is melon, chocolate, strawberry, durian, and original. Once suwar-suwir production, UD Mutiara Rasa requires 80 kg of tape singkong and 42 kg of sugar. In normal events, UD Mutiara Rasa produces up to 14x production per month, so that the needs tape singkong as much as 1,120 kg and sugar as much as 588 kg. The production process of suwar-suwir UD Mutiara Rasa was carried out in several stages.

First, separate the tape singkong with its wicks or fibers so that during the cooking process there are no fibers mixed. Second, weigh the tape singkong and sugar that will be produced so that the amount matches the amount to be produced. Third, mix the tape singkong dough with sugar so that it is fused at the time of production until it becomes suwar-suwir dough. Fourth, cook the dough until cooked until it is suwar-suwir, usually the color of the dough will change color when it is cooked. color before processing is white, when processed the color will change to brown. The process of cooking these suwar-suwir takes approximately 2 hours. Fifth, mixing food coloring, food bleach and fruit flavoring if producing suwar-suwir lapis, but if producing suwar-suwir original is not needed food coloring, food bleach, and fruit flavorings. Sixth, stir the suwar-suwir dough until evenly distributed and then form in accordance with the existing roll table and cut according to size. Seventh, do bindery suwar-suwir per seed with main plastic. Eighth, do the packaging process the company wants as well as by labelling or sticker to be marketed to consumers. The total production cost of UD Mutiara Rasa can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Total Production Costs UD Mutiara Rasa

Types of Products	Total Cost
Suwar-Suwir Original	Rp 2.038.795
Mica Packaging 500 Grams	
Suwar-Suwir Original	Rp 2.069.635
Standing Pouch Packaging 350 Grams	
Suwar-Suwir Lapis	Rp 2.063.450
Mica Packaging 1 Kg	
Suwar-Suwir Lapis	Rp 2.043.980
Mica Packaging 500 Gram	

Calculation of Target Costing

The following stages will be carried out to achieve the objectives of applying the target costing method:

1. Determine the target selling price of the product by looking at the market price.
2. Determine the expected profit target per unit of production.
3. Calculate the amount of the target cost.

Value engineering is an effort to identify various ways that can be used to reduce production costs or reduce production costs (in this study, value engineering is limited only to what is owned by producers, both recipes and packaging).

Target sales price suwar-suwir product UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa determined after making a price comparison with suwar-suwir products from competitors. The list price suwar-suwir product of UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa can be seen in Table 3 and Table 4.

Table 3. List Prices of Suwar-Suwir Products UD Purnama Jati

Types of Products	Price
Suwar-Suwir Lapis	Rp 31.000
Mica Packaging 1 Kg	
Suwar-Suwir Lapis	Rp 19.000
Mica Packaging 500 Gram	

The desired profit target of UD Purnama Jati is 30% of the selling price per unit.

Table 4. List Prices of Suwar-Suwir Products UD Mutiara Rasa

Types of Products	Price
Suwar-Suwir Original	Rp 21.000
Mica Packaging 500 Gram	
Suwar-Suwir Original	Rp 19.000
Standing Pouch Packaging 350 Gram	
Suwar-Suwir Lapis	Rp 34.000
Mica Packaging 1 Kg	
Suwar-Suwir Lapis	Rp 22.000
Mica Packaging 500 Gram	

The desired profit target of UD Mutiara Rasa is 20% of the selling price per unit.

Target Costs of Suwar-Suwir Products

After determining the profit target, then the cost target can be determined after the selling price is reduced by the profit target. On target costing the fulfillment of profit targets is something that must be done so that the method is successful. The target cost suwar-suwir product of UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa can be seen in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5. Target Costs of Suwar-Suwir Products UD. Purnama Jati

Types of Products	Target Cost
Suwar-Suwir Lapis Mica Packaging 1 Kg	Rp 1.345.400
Suwar-Suwir Lapis The Mica Packaging 500 Gram	Rp 1.330.000

Table 6. Target Costs of Suwar-Suwir Products UD Mutiara Rasa

Types of Products	Target Cost
Suwar-Suwir Original Mica Packaging 500 Grams	Rp 2.016.000
Suwar-Suwir Original Standing Pouch Packaging 350 Grams	Rp 2.052.000
Suwar-Suwir Lapis Mica Packaging 1 Kg	Rp 2.040.000
Suwar-Suwir Lapis Mica Packaging 500 Grams	Rp 2.024.000

Value Engineering

After getting the target costs listed above, the production costs that are in accordance with the predetermined cost targets use the target costing tool namely value engineering. Production costs after cost efficiency through value engineering at UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa can be seen in Table 7 and Table 8.

Table 7. Production Costs after Value Engineering at UD Purnama Jati

Types of Products	Production Cost
Suwar-Suwir Lapis Mica Packaging 1 Kg	Rp 1.338.290
Suwar-Suwir Lapis Mica Packaging 500 Gram	Rp 1.329.900

Table 8. Production Costs after Value Engineering at UD Mutiara Rasa

Types of Products	Production Cost
Suwar-Suwir Original Mica Packaging 500 Grams	Rp 2.015.462
Suwar-Suwir Original Standing Pouch Packaging 350 Grams	Rp 2.035.052
Suwar-Suwir Lapis Mica Packaging 1 Kg	Rp 2.038.075
Suwar-Suwir Lapis Mica Packaging 500 Grams	Rp 2.022.355

4. ANALYSIS AND REVIEW

The data that has been obtained are analyzed and then compared with changes in the total costs incurred. Data on production costs of UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa will be compared with alternative costs from the author with the target costing method. Comparison of the production costs of UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa can be seen in Table 9 and Table 10.

Table 9. Comparison of UD Purnama Jati Production Costs

Types of Products	UD		
	Purnama Jati Production Costs	Production Costs after Efficiency	Cost Efficiency
SS Lapis Mica Packaging 1 Kg	Rp1.353.570	Rp 1.338.290	Rp15.280
SS Lapis Mica Packaging 500 Grams	Rp1.343.400	Rp 1.329.900	Rp13.500

Table 10. Comparison of UD Mutiara Rasa Production Costs

Types of Products	UD Mutiara Rasa Production Costs	Production Costs after Efficiency	Cost Efficiency
SS Original Mica Packaging 500 Grams	Rp2.038.795	Rp2.015.462	Rp23.333
SS Original Standing Pouch Packaging 350 Grams	Rp2.069.635	Rp2.035.052	Rp34.583
SS Lapis Mica Packaging 1 Kg	Rp2.063.450	Rp2.038.075	Rp25.375
SS Lapis Mica Packaging 500 Grams	Rp2.043.980	Rp2.022.355	Rp21.625

Based on the data above shows that the successful implementation of the target costing method in UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa. The existence of this method, the two companies can manage their production costs carefully and well. The expected profit target of UD Purnama Jati is 30% and UD Mutiara Rasa of 20% of the selling price per unit can also be achieved using the target costing method. The author tries to reduce production costs by looking for other alternatives, namely replacing the ingredients in the cost component with cheaper materials without reducing the taste and quality of the suwar-suwir products.

At UD Purnama Jati, suwar-suwir lapis product the mica packaging 1 kg total production cost is reduced by Rp 15.280 and suwar-suwir lapis product the mica packaging 500 grams total production cost is reduced by Rp 13.500. At UD Mutiara Rasa, suwar-suwir original product the mica packaging 500 gram total production cost is reduced by Rp 23.333, suwar-suwir original product the standing pouch packaging 350 gram total production cost is reduced by Rp 34.583, suwar-suwir lapis product the mica packaging 1 kg total production cost is reduced by Rp 25.375, and suwar-suwir lapis product the mica packaging 500 gram total production cost is reduced by Rp 21.625.

Based on value engineering which is a tool of the target costing method, UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa can manage and plan how to design products in such a way by starting

from replacing the factors that affect the high costs incurred in the previous product design, up to achievement of desired profit. The target costing method helps in re-examine the cost components high needs to be considered again. Such as the target price calculated based on information from customers and competitors becomes a benchmark and makes it easier for UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa to determine the standardization of product prices and quality. Through cost control, the implementation of target costing is done by identifying the desired selling price and designing products that are willing to be paid by consumers without forgetting the profit target expected by UD Purnama Jati by 30% of each product unit and 20% of the profit target from each unit of product expected by UD Mutiara Rasa.

From the description above, the authors recommend the application of the target costing method in UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa so that they can be used as a basis for determining the selling price and can be used to manage their production costs. The author also hopes that by determining the selling price that has been determined based on market prices, suwar-suwir products from UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa are able to compete with competitors and get the expected profit targets so that UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa can continue to grow and more advanced.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research conducted on UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa shows that with the application of target costing through value engineering, the two companies can still benefit from the selling price per unit as they wish, which is 30% at UD Purnama Teak and 20% at UD Mutiara Rasa. So, if UD Purnama Jati and UD Mutiara Rasa want to increase the selling price of their suwar-suwir products, then the two companies will get a greater profit. Thus, it can be concluded that the implementation of target costing in this study shows success because the two companies can determine the lowest selling price among the current market prices, but they still make the desired profit and can manage production costs well.

Based on the results of calculations that have been compared with production costs prior to the implementation of target costing shows

that the two companies can obtain efficiency in production costs. At UD Purnama Jati, cost efficiency suwar-suwir lapis product the mica packaging 1 kg total production cost is reduced by Rp 15.280 and the mica packaging 500 grams total production cost is reduced by Rp 13.500. At UD Mutiara Rasa, cost efficiency suwar-suwir original product the mica packaging 500 gram total production cost is reduced by Rp 23.333 and the standing pouch packaging 350 gram total production cost is reduced by Rp 34.583, and cost efficiency suwar-suwir lapis product the mica packaging 1 kg total production cost is reduced by Rp 25.375 and the mica packaging 500 gram total production cost is reduced by Rp 21.625.

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